

Investigation of Medical, Medicinal, Clinical and Pharmaceutical Applications of Estradiol, Mestranol (Norlutin), Norethindrone (NET), Norethisterone Acetate (NETA), Norethisterone Enanthate (NETE) and Testosterone Nanoparticles as Biological Imaging, Cell Labeling, Anti-Microbial Agents and Anti-Cancer Nano Drugs in Nanomedicines Based Drug Delivery Systems for Anti-Cancer Targeting and Treatment

Alireza Heidari¹

Faculty of Chemistry, California South University, 14731 Comet St. Irvine, CA 92604, USA.

Abstract

There has been great interest on the selective and efficient biological imaging, cell labeling, anti-microbial agents and anti-cancer Nano drugs in nanomedicines based drug delivery systems for anti-cancer targeting and treatment. Medical, medicinal, clinical and pharmaceutical applications of Estradiol, Mestranol (Norgestrel), Norethindrone (NET), Norethisterone Acetate (NETA), Norethisterone Enanthate (NETE) and Testosterone nanoparticles as biological imaging, cell labeling, anti-microbial agents and anti-cancer Nano drugs is known to occur in several pathways leading to nanomedicines based drug delivery systems for anti-cancer targeting and treatment.

Keywords: Anti-Cancer Nano Drugs, Anti-Microbial Agents, Biological Imaging, Cell Labeling, Estradiol, Drug Delivery Systems, Mestranol (Norlutin), Nanomedicines, Nanoparticles, Norethindrone (NET), Norethisterone Acetate (NETA), Norethisterone Enanthate (NETE), Targeting, Testosterone, Treatment.

¹E-mail: Scholar.Researcher.Scientist@gmail.com; Alireza.Heidari@calsu.us

1. Introduction

There has been great interest on the selective and efficient biological imaging, cell labeling, anti-microbial agents and anti-cancer Nano drugs in nanomedicines based drug delivery systems for anti-cancer targeting and treatment. Medical, medicinal, clinical and pharmaceutical applications of Estradiol, Mestranol (Norlutin), Norethindrone (NET), Norethisterone Acetate (NETA), Norethisterone Enanthate (NETE) and Testosterone nanoparticles (Figure 1) as biological imaging, cell labeling, anti-microbial agents and anti-cancer Nano drugs is known to occur in several pathways leading to nanomedicines based drug delivery systems for anti-cancer targeting and treatment. [1–45]

This editorial aimed to combine these two important applications by the selective reduction of Oxygen electrocatalyzed with modified nanostructures for the co-generation of Hydrogen Peroxide (H_2O_2) and electricity in human cancer cells. The first type electrocatalysts employed was Carbon nanoparticles chemically grafted with Anthraquinone derivatives. The rate of the reduction reaction was calculated to be several orders of magnitude higher than that of unmodified surfaces. The yield of peroxide production was close to 100% in alkaline solutions. [46–90]

2. Results and Discussion

The second type of catalysts was size-controlled Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles. These nanoparticles catalyze Oxygen reduction in a potential dependence two-step process. This fantastic property was only observed for these nanoparticles and thus selective and efficient reduction of Oxygen can be achieved. Hence, the final product of the reduction (i.e. water or Hydrogen Peroxide (H_2O_2)) can be controlled by controlling the electrode potential. In this editorial, our latest results on the applications of nanomaterials for the medical, medicinal, clinical and pharmaceutical applications of Estradiol, Mestranol (Norlutin), Norethindrone (NET), Norethisterone Acetate (NETA), Norethisterone Enanthate (NETE) and Testosterone nanoparticles as biological imaging, cell labeling,

anti-microbial agents and anti-cancer Nano drugs in nanomedicines based drug delivery systems for anti-cancer targeting and treatment will be described. Mechanism for these reactions will be proposed and possible applications in human cancer cells will be discussed.

Due to chemical inertness and low melting point, Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles were previously considered as a catalyst with poor activity [1–90]. However, highly dispersed Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles over various Metal Oxides, such as Iron(III) Oxide (Fe_2O_3), Iridium(IV) Oxide (IrO_2), Rhodium(III) Oxide (Rh_2O_3), Ruthenium(IV) Oxide (RuO_2) and Titanium Dioxide (TiO_2), could possess a dramatically improved activity for low-temperature CO oxidation. Furthermore, the catalytic properties of these Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles catalysts depend on many factors including: type of support, preparation method and in particular, on the size of the Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles clusters. In recent works, it has been shown that small Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles may be stabilized via inserting Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles into cages of Estradiol, Mestranol (Norlutin), Norethindrone (NET), Norethisterone Acetate (NETA), Norethisterone Enanthate (NETE) and Testosterone nanoparticles as biological imaging, cell labeling, anti-microbial agents and anti-cancer Nano drugs in nanomedicines based drug delivery systems for anti-cancer targeting and treatment [1–90].

Further works on different kinds of Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles/Estradiol, Mestranol (Norlutin), Norethindrone (NET), Norethisterone Acetate (NETA), Norethisterone Enanthate (NETE) and Testosterone have been performed for NO reduction and CO oxidation. In the present editorial, Estradiol, Mestranol (Norlutin), Norethindrone (NET), Norethisterone Acetate (NETA), Norethisterone Enanthate (NETE) and Testosterone were used as a support for Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles. The substrate was synthesized by hydrothermal method. After drying at $184^\circ C$ overnight, the sample calcined in a flow of Nitrogen at $760^\circ C$ for 1h. For the Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles loading

process, calcined Estradiol, Mestranol (Norlutin), Norethindrone (NET), Norethisterone Acetate (NETA), Norethisterone Enanthate (NETE) and Testosterone was directly reacted with the Tetrachloroauric(III) acid trihydrate 99% solution,

which was pre-adjusted to the desired pH using a 0.5N solution of NaOH. The solution was prepared by dissolving pure Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles in HCl-HNO₃ mixture (3:1 ratio; respectively). [1–90]

Figure 1. Molecular structure of (a) Estradiol, (b) Mestranol (Norlutin), (c) Norethindrone (NET), (d) Norethisterone Acetate (NETA), (e) Norethisterone Enanthate (NETE) and (f) Testosterone nanoparticles. [1–90]

Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles loading process was performed in a shaker oven, which was equipped with an end over end mixer at 95°C for 36h. After filtering, washing and drying, the resulted catalyst was characterized using Energy Dispersive X-Ray Analysis (EDXA), Energy Dispersive X-Ray Microanalysis (EDXMA), Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM), Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) analysis, X-Ray Diffraction (XRD), Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM), Differential Thermal Analysis–Thermal Gravim Analysis (DTA–TGA), Energy–Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDX), ¹HNMR, ¹³CNMR, UV–Vis, HR–Mass, Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR–FTIR) and FT–Raman spectroscopies data indicated that the Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles were deposited on the surface of the Estradiol, Mestranol (Norlutin), Norethindrone (NET), Norethisterone Acetate (NETA), Norethisterone Enanthate (NETE) and Testosterone. Catalytic activity of the sample was tested in an in house designed U–shape flow reactor. CO oxidation was carried out in a flow rate of 55ml/min under an atmospheric pressure and controlled temperature. A feed stream of 3% CO/Dry air was used to perform reactor tests. The effect of Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles precursor pH on the CO conversion was investigated and determined that the optimum solution pH for this oxidation was 7.3. This means that 53% conversion and hence this catalyst activity for the present purpose is rather high. [1–90]

3. Conclusions

It can be concluded that highly dispersed Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles over various Metal Oxides, such as Iron(III) Oxide (Fe₂O₃), Iridium(IV) Oxide (IrO₂), Rhodium(III) Oxide (Rh₂O₃), Ruthenium(IV) Oxide (RuO₂) and Titanium Dioxide (TiO₂), could possess a dramatically improved activity for low–temperature CO oxidation. Furthermore, the catalytic properties of these Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles catalysts depend on many factors including: type of support, preparation method and in particular, on the size of the Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles clusters. In addition, it has been shown that small Cadmium

Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles may be stabilized via inserting Cadmium Oxide (CdO) nanoparticles into cages of Estradiol, Mestranol (Norlutin), Norethindrone (NET), Norethisterone Acetate (NETA), Norethisterone Enanthate (NETE) and Testosterone nanoparticles as biological imaging, cell labeling, anti–microbial agents and anti–cancer Nano drugs in nanomedicines based drug delivery systems for anti–cancer targeting and treatment.

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